

GTP hydrolysis drives microtubule growth in dynamic instability: Revisiting overlooked observations

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Abstract

The spatiotemporal organization of microtubules (MTs) is fundamental to cellular function. Since its discovery four decades ago, dynamic instability (DI) has been extensively investigated as the core mechanism driving this organization, with the GTP-cap model serving as the prevailing framework for the data interpretation. However, accumulating evidence suggests a need to re-evaluate this paradigm. Key unresolved questions include how MTs elongate below the critical concentration for spontaneous nucleation, whether GMPCPP-tubulin (Tb) truly mimics the GTP-Tb in the growth phase, and whether protofilament (pf) curvature remains independent of the growing/shrinking phase. This Review provides a comprehensive resolution to these paradoxes by re-analyzing existing data through new conceptual lenses, ultimately predicting a GTPase-coupled MT growth in DI.

Introduction.

Microtubules (MTs) are one of the major cytoskeletal structures in eucaryotes. They are stiff, hollow tubes typically containing 13 protofilaments (pfs) formed through self-assembly of $\alpha\beta$ -tubulin (Tb) heterodimers that join longitudinally in a head-to-tail fashion. Grown *in vitro*, both ends of MTs exhibit stochastic transition between periods of slow growth and rapid shrinkage, a behavior known as ‘dynamic instability’ today (*Bowne-Anderson et al. , 2013, Brouhard and Rice, 2018, Knossow et al. , 2020*). The study on dynamic instability (hereafter DI) started by the pioneering work of Mitchison and Kirschner, who discovered that growing and shrinking populations coexist in bulk MT solution (*Mitchison and Kirschner, 1984*). Microtubule DI plays a critical role in chromosome movement and separation during mitosis (*Kirschner and Mitchison, 1986, Mimori-Kiyosue and Tsukita, 2003*).

More than 40 years have passed since the discovery of the DI phenomenon, and significant progress has been made in understanding how MT dynamics are controlled in cells through interactions with MAPs. However, the molecular mechanisms of DI remain poorly understood, despite its importance in both cell biology and polymer physics. Not a few reviews have been published on DI, summarizing dynamics, structural findings, and biochemical data (nucleotide states)(*Bowne-Anderson et al. , 2013, Desai and Mitchison, 1997, Gudimchuk and McIntosh, 2021, Manka and Moores, 2018a*). In those reviews, the “standard model” of DI implicates a “cap” of GTP-bound Tb dimers at the growing MT end as the main determinant of MT stability. Loss of the GTP-cap switches MT from growth phase to shrink phase (catastrophe). Physically, the MT length history during DI is not time-reversal invariant, so it cannot be an equilibrium phenomenon. To maintain this process in a steady state, a non-equilibrium driving, i.e., a GTPase, is essential. In the above model, the energy released during GTP hydrolysis is used to destabilize the MT structure, driving the transition from growth to shrinkage (catastrophe).

Like many previous reviews, this paper aims to elucidate the molecular mechanisms of DI, however, from a unique perspective. We reorganize previous research findings along the Tb concentration scale. The overview is presented hierarchically, covering the spatial scales of MT (nucleation, disappearance; elongation and contraction) (Part I), of pf (curvature change) (Part II), and of individual Tbs and their GTPase-coupled processes (Part III). In Part I at the MT level, we summarize the Tb concentration range at which spontaneous nucleation occurs, the one at which seeds are required for MT growth, and the one at which DI is observed. Next, in Part II, at the resolution of pf, we show the results from different cryo-EM and cryo-ET studies of growing MT ends *in vitro*, which appear to be controversial at a glance (*Chrétien et al. , 1995, Mandelkow et al. , 1991, McIntosh et al. , 2018*), are consistent if they are sorted by Tb concentration. Then in Part III, at the resolution of Tb, we summarize experimental findings on how the relationship between GTPases and MT growth changes with Tb concentration. It becomes clear that there are fundamentally distinct ranges of Tb concentrations, the one in which MTs grow without GTP hydrolysis, and the other in which MTs grow in synchrony with GTP hydrolysis. Having established this relationship, we will question whether GMPCPP-Tb actually mimics GTP-Tb at the Tb concentration at which DI occurs, as has often been said so far. Finally in Part IV, based on the above overview and reconsideration, we propose an alternative perspective for DI, where, at the Tb concentrations DI occurs, GTP hydrolysis is necessary for MT growth, not the cause of the catastrophe as assumed in the GTPcap model. In the following discussion we will not consider DI at the minus ends, which are normally anchored in the cells and have fewer physiological roles than the plus ends. Furthermore, rescue events are rarely observed *in vitro* (*Walker et al. , 1988*), so we will also not consider them.

I. Tb-concentration dependence of MT dynamics

This part deals with the results at the scales accessible by optical means (turbidity measurements and optical microscopy). See Fig. 2 for a summary.

I-1. Spontaneous nucleation and growth of MT occur only above critical concentration, C_{c2} .

Spontaneous MT polymerization does not occur unless the Tb concentration is above a certain level. The minimum Tb concentration required for MT formation (critical concentration C_{c2}) can be experimentally determined as follows: A Tb solution containing sufficient concentrations of Mg^{2+} ions and GTP is prepared. The temperature is increased, and then the amount of polymer is measured through turbidity or viscosity. After a short undetectable period, the amount of polymer gradually increases (i.e., spontaneous nucleation occurs), eventually reaching a steady state as the free Tb concentration approaches C_{c2} (Fig. 1C)(*Gaskin et al. , 1974*). The steady-state polymer mass increases linearly with the initial Tb concentration C_0 (Fig. 1D). The critical Tb concentration C_{c2} required for polymerization can be determined from the intercept of this plot. The C_{c2} of bovine brain Tb measured in BRB buffer (80 mM Pipes pH 6.8, 1 mM GTP, 1 mM EGTA, 1 mM $MgCl_2$) is 15-20 μM (*Mitchison and Kirschner, 1984, Wieczorek et al. , 2015*); MT polymerization does not occur if the initial concentration C_0 is lower than this concentration. The state in which MTs coexist in a constant concentration of GTP-Tb is maintained by the (free) energy released by GTP hydrolysis and is not a state of thermal equilibrium.

Naturally C_{c2} is not an intrinsic property of Tb, but rather is a system parameter that is dependent on the solution condition (buffer, pH, ionic strength, divalent cations, temperature, etc.)(*Mirigian et al. , 2013*) and the ligand bound to Tb. For example, the C_{c2} of the system containing glycerol (*Voter and Erickson, 1984*) being 3 μM is smaller than the C_{c2} for BRB buffer. The C_{c2} of GMPCPP-bound Tb is also much smaller than that of GTP-Tb (*Hyman et al. , 1992*)(detailed in Part II). C_{c2} is also affected by ligands such as vinblastine and taxol. The experiments described below (Fig. 1C–1K) were all performed in BRB buffer or equivalent solutions, and the C_{c2} values were nearly the same (Supplementary Table 1).

Fig. 1 Tb concentration-dependence of MT polymerization dynamics.

(A, B) Schematic representation of dynamic instability. (A) In a typical representation, a MT is shown to go between growing and shortening phase. (B) Actual growth of MT starts with a seed, ends up in a catastrophe and shortening. At low Tb concentrations, it is a sporadic one-off process, repeated over time. (C, D) Properties of MT polymerization in bulk solution. (C) Polymerization time courses of MT solutions with various initial Tb concentrations, monitored by OD350. (D) The plateau values of the graphs in (C) plotted against Tb concentration. The data form a straight line, and the X-intercept indicates the Tb concentration (C_{c2}) required for polymerization. (E, F) Changes in the number and length of MTs after dilution of a MT solution to a concentration below C_{c2} (adapted from (Mitchison and Kirschner, 1984)). Prior to the experiment, long MTs (average length = $\sim 18 \mu\text{m}$) were prepared in the concentration above C_{c2} , and the solution of these actively growing MTs was excessively diluted with Tb solutions at 15 μM ($= C_{c2}$) or 7.5 μM . (E) The time course of MT number concentration (x and + is for 15 μM and 7.5 μM , respectively) and (F) the MT length distribution before and after dilution were measured. In (E), the faint red and blue lines are meant to guide the viewer's eyes. Three bar graphs in (F) show the MT lengths fixed before dilution (top), 10 minutes after dilution with 15 μM Tb solution (middle), 10 minutes after dilution with 7.5 μM Tb (bottom). For comparison, the copy of the pre-dilution data (blue bars) is placed behind the post-dilution data (yellow bars) in middle and bottom. (G-K) Behavior of individual MT filaments. (G) Polymerization of an individual MT filament, spontaneously nucleated at Tb

concentration near C_{c2} (adapted from (Horio and Hotani, 1986)). Time course of the MT plus-end position was recorded under a dark-field microscope. (H-K) Behavior of MTs polymerized onto a flagellar axoneme (Walker *et al.*, 1988). (H) Tb concentration dependence of MT growth rate, (I) shortening rate and (J) catastrophe frequency. In panel (H) and (J), the + and - symbols indicate the plus and minus end, respectively. In panel (I), mean values for plus end are indicated by solid circles and mean values for minus ends are indicated by triangles. (K) Tb concentration dependence of the percentage of seeds having MTs. After placing axonemes in a Tb solution for 15 minutes, the percentage of axonemes with MTs from one end (●) and from both ends (○) was measured. As the Tb concentration approaches the point where catastrophe is suppressed (graph J, blue arrow), all seeds have MTs on both ends (graph K, blue arrow).

I-2. Dynamic Instability in single MT filaments occurs below C_{c2} .

The discovery of the phenomenon now known as DI dates to the work of Mitchison and Kirschner *et al.* (Mitchison and Kirschner, 1984)(hereafter, M&K). They found that when they diluted the solution in the experimental system described above in Part I-1 just before reaching steady state and the concentration of free Tb dropped below a critical concentration, C_{c2} , the total number of MTs in solution gradually decreased (Fig. 1E), but that among the remaining MTs, some were elongating while others were shortening (Fig. 1F). Because the technology to observe MT dynamics in real time under an optical microscope was unavailable at the time, they fixed the solution at regular intervals after dilution and measured the MT length using an electron microscope. Although they could not determine whether the same MTs underwent both processes, they observed a tendency for the reaction, whether elongating or shortening, to persist once initiated. In separate experiments, they showed that the rate of elongation increased linearly with Tb concentration, while shortening was more rapid than elongation and independent of Tb concentration. They predicted that individual MTs elongate and shorten, alternating between the two phases, a phenomenon they termed dynamic instability (DI).

A couple of years later, the dynamics of individual MTs were visualized in real time under the dark-field microscopy (Horio and Hotani, 1986). The authors observed the spontaneously nucleating MTs in Tb solution at near the critical concentration C_{c2} (Fig. 1G). By using optical microscope, the appearance of two phases on a single MT, slow elongation followed by rapid shortening, was confirmed. Their experiment required a fine-tuning of Tb concentration: if the concentration was too high, the MTs would be obscured by a nucleation haze, and if the Tb concentration was too low, MTs would not form at all.

I-3. Without seed no MT can grow below C_{c2}

It is Walker *et al.* (Walker *et al.*, 1988) who developed an experimental system that is now widely used to analyze DI. Using flagellar axonemes as seed, they succeeded to make a single MT repeat polymerization and depolymerization under differential interference contrast microscope, and measured the parameters that characterize DI, such as polymerization/depolymerization rates and catastrophe/rescue frequency (Fig. 1H–K).

Many papers today show a figure similar to Fig. 1A to schematize the DI phenomenon. But to the author's knowledge, there has been no report of pure MTs stably alternating between two phases without seeds at Tb concentration below C_{c2} . Therefore, Fig. 1B, rather than Fig. 1A, is probably appropriate. Retrospectively after the establishment of Walker's experimental system, that some MTs continued to elongate in M&K's solution diluted below C_{c2} can be understood as the consequence of MTs that had been elongated before dilution temporarily acting as seeds. Since M&K's experimental system did not contain MTs that are stable below C_{c2} , such as axonemes, MTs that began depolymerization extinct, and the number of MTs gradually decreased (Fig. 1E). Even in Walker *et al.*'s experimental system involving seeds, the lower the Tb concentration, the longer the period of silence in which there is no MT growing or shrinking

on the seed. The more accurate description of DI would, therefore, be "repetition of a transient elongation and shortening, with each growth phase induced by a seed."

There is a lower limit, C_{c1} , for the concentration at which MTs can elongate in the presence of a seed (Fig. 1H). Walker *et al.* found that the critical concentration required for MT elongation at both the plus and minus ends is $5.5 \mu\text{M}$. Hereafter, this lower limit is referred to as C_{c1} (Fig. 1H, red arrow), to distinguish it from C_{c2} (Fig. 1D, blue arrow). Above C_{c1} , the elongation rate increases nearly linearly with concentration, whereas the shortening rate remains constant regardless of Tb concentration (Fig. 1I), consistent with the electron microscopy results of M&K.

In pure Tb solutions with concentrations below C_{c2} , the fact that MTs emerge (only) from seeds and the fact that the steady-state concentration of MTs there is zero (Fig. 1D) are compatible: When a certain number of seeds are introduced into an abundant Tb solution with a concentration below C_{c2} , the total amount of MTs emerging in steady state is proportional to the number of seeds (for example, Fig. 4 in (Jonasson *et al.*, 2020)), but not proportional to the amount of Tb solution prepared.

I-4. C_{c2} has different facets.

C_{c2} is the concentration at which spontaneous nucleation begins and at which the DI catastrophe disappears. In the measurements by Walker *et al.* mentioned above, the frequency with which growing MTs fell into catastrophe gradually decreased with increasing Tb concentration, and catastrophes became rare, if any, at concentrations above $15 \mu\text{M}$ (Fig. 1J). Walker *et al.* stated, "we were unable to analyze the kinetics of MT growth at Tb concentrations $> 15.5 \mu\text{M}$ because extensive self-nucleated MT assembly obscured the field of view, making analysis of individual, seeded MTs impossible." Therefore, this concentration of $15 \mu\text{M}$ is likely close to C_{c2} (see Appendix I-4-1).

The picture of switching between catastrophe regime and spontaneous nucleation regime near C_{c2} is reinforced by Tb concentration dependence of the proportion of seeds bearing MTs (Fig. 1K): This proportion increased sigmoidally with increasing Tb concentration below C_{c2} , and upon approaching the critical concentration C_{c2} , all seeds germinated MTs. While Fig. 1K shows data from Walker *et al.* using axoneme fragments as seeds, Wieczorek *et al.* have also reported similar results using MTs grown from various kinds of seeds, including centrosomes, GMPCPP MTs, and axonemes (Wieczorek *et al.*, 2015); while the C_{c2} for spontaneous nucleation was $22 \mu\text{M}$, MTs germinated from all seeds at $20 \mu\text{M}$ when seeds are introduced. They also showed that adding a factor that inhibits catastrophe allowed MTs to germinate from all seeds even at lower concentrations.

Fig. 2 summarizes the contents of Part I except that we postpone to Part III the explanation of the rightmost panel, that corresponds to the region with the highest Tb concentration. In essence, DI is inseparable from seed-dependent elongation. For more than 40 years of DI research, why MTs below the critical concentration C_{c2} can elongate if MT seeds are present has not been a major issue, probably because "catastrophe" is so spectacular that people's interest has focused on the mechanism that triggers depolymerization.

Fig.2 Tb concentration dependence of MT dynamics.

The intensity of the background blue color in each panel represents the Tb concentration. **(A)** At Tb concentrations below C_{c1} , no polymerization occurs. **(B)** At Tb concentrations between C_{c1} and C_{c2} , MTs started from seeds exhibit dynamic instability. As the Tb concentration increases, the catastrophe becomes less frequent. **(C)** At concentrations above C_{c2} , MTs can spontaneously polymerize from Tb solution. The number of MTs generated by spontaneous nucleation increases in proportion to the power of the Tb concentration (Voter and Erickson, 1984). **(D)** At concentrations far above C_{c2} , many short MTs rapidly form in a very short time. About this highest concentration range, we will describe more in Part II.

II. Tb-concentration dependence of MT tip structure

In this section, we investigate the morphology of pfs at the tips of MTs as they elongate or shrink, at electron microscopy resolution, as functions of Tb concentration in solution.

II-1. There is no tight link between Tb conformation and its nucleotide state.

Tb dimers inside MT lattices form pfs with a curvature of approximately 0 degree, and the Tb conformation there is described as "straight" (Löwe *et al.*, 2001, Nogales *et al.*, 1998). From the late 1980s to the early 1990s, several studies examining the shape of MT tips by electron microscopy (Mandelkow *et al.*, 1991, Melki *et al.*, 1989) fostered the expectation of a tight link between the nucleotide state and the Tb dimer form: GTP-Tb would lead to polymerization by adopting a polymerization-compatible "straight" form in solution, while GDP-Tb would lead to depolymerization by its "curved" form after GTP hydrolysis (on the β -Tb of the dimer). Indeed, Mandelkow *et al.*'s cryo-electron images showed that the tip of actively polymerizing MTs had a blunt or tapered shape with an array of straight pfs, while the tip of depolymerizing MTs had radially curved pfs (Fig. 3A, D) (Mandelkow *et al.*, 1991).

However, subsequent observations are not consistent with the above scenario. Crystal structures of the Tb complex with depolymerization factor (Ayaz *et al.*, 2012, Gigant *et al.*, 2000, Nawrotek *et al.*, 2011, Pecqueur *et al.*, 2012, Prota *et al.*, 2013, Ravelli *et al.*, 2004), biochemical analyses of Tb binding affinity to ligands and proteins (Ayaz *et al.*, 2012, Barbier *et al.*, 2010, Honnappa *et al.*, 2003), and structural analysis by small-angle X-ray scattering spectroscopy of Tb (Rice *et al.*, 2008), all suggest that Tb in solution is curved whether the bound nucleotide is GTP or GDP (see Appendix II-1-1). Furthermore, molecular dynamics simulations (Grafmüller and Voth, 2011, Peng *et al.*, 2014) also predict that free Tb in solution fluctuates over a wide range (intradimer rotation = 0–20 degrees) from "straight" to curved

states, regardless of whether the bound nucleotide is GTP or GDP. In future discussions, we will refer to the conformation of Tb in solution as "curved" in contrast to the "straight" conformation of Tb in the MT lattice, but "curved" does not imply a specific angle.

There has been much interest in the transient changes from the "curved" GTP-Tb in solution until the "straight" Tb fitted into the MT lattice. In the following Part II-2, 3, and 4, we will focus on the variable morphology of the MT tip.

Fig. 3 The curvature of the pfs at the growing/shrinking end of MTs.

(A–C) CryoEM images of the growing end of MTs. All three experiments were performed in the same buffer solution, but with an initial Tb concentration, C_0 , of 50 μM (A) (Mandelkow *et al.*, 1991), 13.5 μM (B) (Chrétien *et al.*, 1995) and 20 μM (C) (McIntosh *et al.*, 2018). (D–F) Cryo-EM images of the shrinking end of MTs, induced by dilution of the solution. Panels (D), (E), (F) are obtained from the same respective sources as in (A), (B), and (C). All panels are shown at the same scale (Scale bar in panel A; 100 nm). (G, H) Traces of pfs from the growing end of MTs (initial Tb concentration = 20 μM) (G) and the shortening MTs (initial Tb concentration ≈ 3 μM) (H) (McIntosh *et al.*, 2018). (I) Traces of pfs from growing end of MTs. (Gudimchuk *et al.*, 2020). Note that the numbers in the graph titles indicate the total Tb concentrations, not the free Tb concentration. (J) Scattered plots for length and curvature of pfs at the MT proximal end, based on the traces shown in (I) (For detail of the analysis, see BOX1). The pfs having length ≥ 65 nm are represented by red dots. The percentages of the pfs with length ≥ 65 nm is shown in the bar graph. The results of the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test indicated that the curvatures of the pfs with length ≥ 65 nm are significantly smaller than the curvatures of the pfs with length < 65 nm. For 10 μM Tb, $D = 0.65$, $p = 7.22 \times 10^{-5}$; for 20 μM Tb, $D = 0.63$, $p = 2.65 \times 10^{-4}$; for 40 μM Tb, $D = 0.64$, $p = 2.60 \times 10^{-13}$. (K) Summary: Tb concentration dependence of the shape of pfs at the growing-end of MTs. Bold lines represent several pfs viewed in projection. (L) and (M) Enlargement of the boxed area in panel K. For details of the experimental conditions in (A)–(I), see Supplementary Table I. Figures in panel A to I are reproduced with permission from the original papers cited therein.

II-2 Pf at the MT tip becomes straighter with increasing Tb concentration.

Since Mandelkow, several research groups have attempted to investigate the morphology of MT tips using cryoelectric experiments, each of which has reported different images and proposed different polymerization models (for review, see (*Gudimchuk and McIntosh, 2021*)). These results, when correlated with the Tb concentration in the solution, reveal a trend in which the pf at the tip becomes more straight with increasing Tb concentration (a schematic summary is given in Fig. 3K).

In addition to the observations by Mandelkow *et al.* (1991) (Fig. 3A, D) introduced in the previous chapter, there are cryo-EM observations by (*Chrétien et al. , 1995*), Fig. 3B, 3E) and cryo-EM + holography observations by (*McIntosh et al. , 2018*), Fig. 3C, 3F). These three experiments were performed in solutions of almost the same composition (Supplementary Table 1), and these different shapes at MT tips likely reflect their different Tb concentrations. In MTs polymerizing without seed at Tb concentrations well above the critical concentration for polymerization, C_{c2} , shown in Fig. 3A, the pfs at the tips are straight (blunt/tapered), whereas in MTs polymerized from seeds below the critical concentration, C_{c2} , shown in Fig. 3B, C, most of the pfs are curved outward. In Fig. 3B, pfs interact laterally to form a gently curved sheet, while in Fig. 3C, individual pfs are more strongly curved, forming a frayed shape (see Appendix II-2-1). All research groups have reported unanimously that when the solution is diluted to shorten the MTs, the individual pfs at their tip curve outward (Fig. 3D-3F).

The Tb concentration dependence becomes even clearer when examining the statistics of the pf curvature at the MT tip during elongation : In McIntosh *et al.*'s 2018 data (*McIntosh et al. , 2018*), a population of low-curvature pfs extending beyond the tube end of cylindrical MT wall appears only during elongation (Fig. 3G, arrowheads). This makes the pfs of elongating MTs appear more "crested" as compared with those of shortening MTs (Fig. 3H) (Fig. 5G and Fig. 7E in (*McIntosh et al. , 2018*)) (see Appendix II-2-2). This crest is also observed in their 2020 data (*Gudimchuk et al. , 2020*), and appears more pronounced at higher initial Tb concentrations (Fig. 3I; Fig. 5d-f in (*Gudimchuk et al. , 2020*)). When we plotted the data in Fig. 3I in two dimensions with pf curvature axis and length axis, we confirmed that as initial Tb concentration increased, the number of long, straight pfs (shown by red dots in the left three panels and red bands in the right bar graph in Fig. 3J) increased (see Box 2 for details on the relationship between curvature and pf length and the analytical method). It is likely that free Tb concentration also increased in this order. At an initial Tb concentration of 40 μM , nearly 10% of all pfs exceeded 65 nm in length, and the curvature of pfs reaching this length (8.1 ± 4.1 degrees/dimer (mean \pm s.d.)) is comparable to the mean curvature of pf-bundled MT tips reported by Chretien *et al.* (7.8 degrees/dimer) (*Guesdon et al. , 2016*). (cf. The curvatures discussed in this chapter are those measured by projecting the pfs onto the two-dimensional plane of the electron microscope grid. We have not been able to analyze twist, another parameter that describes the original three-dimensional conformation of the pfs.)

In summary, below C_{c2} , pfs are independent and only a small number of pfs are straight. As Tb concentrations approach C_{c2} from below, the proportion of straight pfs increases (*Gudimchuk et al. , 2020, McIntosh et al. , 2018*), and they laterally associate to form gently curved sheets (*Chrétien et al. , 1995, Guesdon et al. , 2016*). Above C_{c2} , pfs that are nearly straight up to their tips predominate, and tapered sheets and blunt tubes are normally seen (*Mandelkow et al. , 1991*). Considering that MTs polymerized from seeds below C_{c2} exhibited a decreased catastrophe frequency with increasing Tb concentration (Part I, Fig. 1J), the decrease in pf curvature with increasing Tb concentration discussed here is the phenomenon along the same line with the decrease in catastrophe frequency.

The concentration-dependent conformational change of proteins is precedent in various proteins (*Ota et al. , 2024, Sakalauskas et al. , 2019, Sato et al. , 2023*). Careful examination of those cases suggests that an increase in Tb concentration might bring about a qualitative change in the intermolecular interactions between Tb dimers, the change which may thermodynamically favor straight pfs, and also straight oligomers in solution (see below II-3).

Fygenson *et al.* have previously investigated the temperature dependence of MT dynamics in relation to the Tb concentration dependence of MT dynamics. They concluded that increases in temperature and concentration have qualitatively similar effects (*Fygenson et al. , 1994*).

It should be noted that catastrophes are also reduced when the curvature of pfs is reduced by factors other than Tb concentration. For example, the addition of taxol, which inhibits catastrophes and promotes polymerization, also straightens pfs (Fig. 6j in (*Gudimchuk et al. , 2020*)) and a small number of protruding long pfs associate laterally to form gently curved bundles ahead of MT wall. Furthermore, when comparing different Tb isotypes, isotypes with lower curvature of the distal pfs exhibit faster MT elongation and lower catastrophe frequency (*Vemu et al. , 2017*).

II-3 Pathway of spontaneous MT nucleation may give a hint about the role of Tb straightening in MT elongation.

The cooccurrence of straight pf and the suppression of catastrophe at the growing tip of MTs below C_{c2} is analogous to the cooccurrence of straight oligomers and spontaneous nucleation above C_{c2} (Fig. 4A, B). In an experiment using *Drosophila* Tb by Ayukawa *et al.* (*Ayukawa et al. , 2021*), spontaneous nucleation occurred above C_{c2} , and many oligomers were formed in the Tb solution, consisting of longitudinally assembled GTP-Tb. Most of these oligomers were curved, but a small proportion (12%) were straight (kink < 4.6 degrees/dimer) (Fig. 4B, yellow highlighted). On the other hand, with the Tb mutant (Y222F) having a mutation in the GTP-binding site of β -Tb, the proportion of straight oligomers increased to 31% of the total. They began to nucleate at a much lower Tb concentration than the wild-type and reached a steady state earlier than the wild-type (Fig. 4A). The same trend was observed in the experiment by Howes *et al.* (*Howes et al. , 2018*) comparing yeast and mammalian Tbs: Yeast Tbs, which have a higher proportion of straight oligomers prior to nucleation, are more likely to undergo nucleation than mammalian Tbs, and the critical concentration C_{c2} of yeast Tb is about one-fifth that of mammalian Tb. In both yeast and mammalian Tbs, the proportion of straight oligomers for GTP oligomers than that for the GDP oligomers, which cannot realize MT nucleation.

Fig. 4 Spontaneous nucleation and oligomer curvature. **(A)** Critical concentration for polymerization. For both WT and the Y222F mutant, the turbidity plateau was a linear function of the initial Tb concentration, yielding the critical concentrations, C_{c2} (= x intercept), of 4.7 and 0.19 μM for WT and Y222F Tb, respectively. **(B)** Distributions of curvatures of WT(GTP), WT(GDP), Y222F(GTP), and Y222F(GDP) oligomers. For reference, the kink in the Tb dimer in MTs (Nogales *et al.*, 1998) is indicated by a blue arrow, and the kink in the Tb dimer in the crystal structure (Brouhard and Rice, 2014) is indicated by a bracket. **(C)** Scheme of the structural pathway of spontaneous nucleation. Panels A and B are copied from Ayukawa *et al.*, *J Cell Biol.* 2021.

Ayukawa *et al.* elucidated the nucleation pathway (Fig. 4C), taking advantage of the active nucleation of the Y222F mutant (Ayukawa *et al.*, 2021). Straight oligomers that reached a certain length (the number being less than 1% of the total oligomers) began to interact laterally, and some of the laterally associated complexes of straight oligomers grew to form broad sheets, while some others closed into MTs. In contrast, the majority of curved oligomers remained single-stranded throughout.

About the mechanism of MT growth at its end the hierarchical nature of spontaneous nucleation (Fig. 4C) provides a clue, which is to be discussed in Part II-4. During both nucleation (Fig. 4C) and MT tip elongation (Fig. 3I, J), only a small fraction of the oligomer/pf population straightens, while the average curvature of GTP-oligomers and that of GDP-oligomers are almost identical (Ayukawa *et al.*, 2021, Howes *et al.*, 2018), and the pfs at MT tip are equally curved whether it is elongating or contracting (McIntosh *et al.*, 2018). The implications of this will be discussed in Part IV.

II-4. Transition from linear to 2D growth is the key to MT growth

Since the pathway of nucleation (Fig. 4C) is based on the dimensional hierarchy of MT structure, where linear pfs are laterally associated to form sheets/tubes, a similar structural hierarchy is expected to underlie the pathway of assembly at the growing end of MTs (Fig. 3). Specifically, Tb in solution first binds to the tips of pfs, increasing their length (1D growth). Then, pfs with low curvature laterally interact to form sheets or MT walls (2D growth). Similar to the mechanism of spontaneous nucleation, straighter the pfs, higher the chance of successful lateral interaction without going into catastrophe, making the MT growth more stable (Part II-2). This contrasts with the outward bending and lateral dissociation of pfs at the end of shrinking MTs (Fig. 3K-M, Fig. 4C).

The effective free energy of lateral binding is roughly estimated to be about $4 k_B T$ per dimer: If we denote by ΔG_{Long} the free energy gain per dimer associated with longitudinal binding along pf, and by ΔG_{Lat} the free energy gain per dimer for lateral binding, then ΔG_{Long} is estimated to be about $-10 k_B T$ based on the population ratio of oligomers of different lengths present in *Drosophila* Tb solution (Ayukawa *et al.*, 2021) (assuming that the longitudinal binding energy of Tb is the same in pf and oligomers (Gardner *et al.*, 2011a, Manka and Moores, 2018a), while $\Delta G_{\text{Long}} + \Delta G_{\text{Lat}}$ is estimated to be about $-14 k_B T$ based on the Tb concentration dependence of MT growth rate (Ayukawa *et al.*, 2021). The difference between the two then gives the above value, $\Delta G_{\text{Lat}} = 4 k_B T$, compensating for the ambiguity of the standard free energy. VanBuren *et al.* (VanBuren *et al.*, 2002) showed that, assuming similar values of ΔG_{Long} and ΔG_{Lat} , a stochastic polymerization model can reproduce DI with growth rate similar to the measured value (Walker *et al.*, 1988). The lateral binding thus enables stable MT growth.

MTs are not the only cytoskeletal filaments whose growth stabilizes as the structure becomes two-dimensional. In actin nucleation, as the actin grows from a monomer to one-dimensional structures and becomes longer than a trimer, the helical arrangement is completed and cross-filament bonds are formed (i.e., two-dimensionalization), stabilizing the structure. A critical nucleus appears to be the smallest protomer with a cross-filament bond (Oda *et al.*, 2016, Rosenbloom *et al.*, 2021, Sept and McCammon, 2001).

II-5. MT growth in vivo

In vivo, a correlation exists between the decrease in the curvature of the MT tip pf and MT growth. Using EM, electron tomography (ET) and fluorescence microscopy, Zovko *et al.* analyzed pericellular MTs in mouse fibroblasts (Zovko *et al.* , 2008). They found that the tips of growing MTs exhibited a variety of shapes, including "frayed" tips, which were dominant in McIntosh *et al.*'s analysis, as well as "flared" and "sheet-straight" tips with lower curvature, and even tips similar to the "blunt" tips reported by Mandelkow *et al.* Addition of nocodazole to cells to induce MT depolymerization increased the proportion of "frayed" tips, and eliminated the sheet-straight tips consisting of straight pfs ((Zovko *et al.* , 2008), Fig. 3) (see Appendix II-5-1). Another group used electron tomography to examine kinetochore MTs in PtK1 cells and *Drosophila* S2 cells. They found that when cells were treated with taxol to promote polymerization, the number of highly curved frayed MT tips decreased, and the number of 'sheets', which are bundles of pfs, and 'blunts', which are rows of straight pfs, increased (VandenBeldt *et al.* , 2006).

However, the local environment of MTs *in vivo* differs from that *in vitro*. While there have been few studies accurately measuring intracellular Tb concentrations, those limited data suggest that intracellular Tb concentrations are not high enough for spontaneous nucleation (Gard and Kirschner, 1987, Hiller and Weber, 1978). At such low concentrations, the curved Tb dimer is stable regardless of whether the bound nucleotide is GTP or GDP. Therefore, a high energy barrier is expected for the transition of GTP-Tb to the straight conformation prerequisite for MT growth (Fig. 3K; leftmost). Indeed, intracellular MTs cannot assemble properly without MAPs (Busch and Brunner, 2004, Komarova *et al.* , 2009, Srayko *et al.* , 2005). For example, blocking the dimerization of the plus end-binding protein EB1 in CHO-K1 cultured cells increases the frequency of catastrophes and results in cells producing only very short MTs (Komarova *et al.* , 2009). During early development in *C. elegans*, the absence of several centrosome components, including γ -Tb, prevents nucleation from the centrosome and leads to abnormal development. Furthermore, factors such as ZYG-9 and TAC-1, which are XMAP orthologs, are essential for astral MT elongation (Srayko *et al.* , 2005).

In vivo, MAPs and other factors help MTs grow in an environment with low Tb concentration. At first, nucleation is achieved by locally enhancing the Tb concentration within the cell. For example, in *C. elegans* centrosomes, a protein called SPD-5 condenses in the pericentriolar matrix, forming compartments through liquid-liquid phase separation (LLPS). Within these compartments, Tb and MAPs are concentrated 4-5 times more than in the cytoplasm, resulting in the nucleation of numerous MTs from the compartments (Woodruff *et al.* , 2017). Similarly, in neurons, the minus-end binding protein CAMPSAP mediates LLPS, leading to the concentration of Tb within these compartments, resulting in nucleation (Imasaki *et al.* , 2022). Furthermore, in cells, MTs elongate from templates such as γ -Tb ring complexes, a manoeuvre which allows to bypass the energy barrier of spontaneous nucleation (i.e., the energy barrier that Tb must overcome to form straight oligomers) (Zheng *et al.* , 1995).

Secondly, +TIPs (various MAPs that bind to the growing end) interact with elongating MTs to escort their growth (for review, see (Akhmanova and Steinmetz, 2015, Lawrence *et al.* , 2023)). Among +TIPs involved in MT growth, those that bind to the leading edge of MTs, along the long axis of pfs (e.g., XMAP and CLASP), enable MT growth at low Tb concentrations by recruiting Tb dimers to the growing edge (Al-Bassam and Chang, 2011). On the other hand, +TIPs that bind to a region proximal to the tubular MT (Ettinger *et al.* , 2016, Guesdon *et al.* , 2016, Nakamura *et al.* , 2012), at the groove where pfs laterally contact each other (e.g., EB,

TPX, DCX) (Fourniol *et al.* , 2010, Zhang *et al.* , 2017), appear to suppress catastrophe by stabilizing lateral interactions. These two types of +TIPs reflect the dimensional hierarchy in MT structure mentioned in Part II-4, and both factors are necessary for the stable growth of MT (Tsuchiya and Goshima, 2021, Zanic *et al.* , 2013) (see Appendix II-5-2).

Also, *in vivo* polymerization in the presence of various MAPs can exhibit qualitatively different behavior and structure from those *in vitro* with pure Tb. This is plausibly a result of Tb's synergetic interactions with various intracellular proteins. MT elongation in cells is several times to an order of magnitude faster than *in vitro*, despite low Tb concentrations (Cassimeris *et al.* , 1988, Komarova *et al.* , 2009, Srayko *et al.* , 2005, Stepanova *et al.* , 2010) (see Appendix II-5-3). Nevertheless, catastrophe and rescue events are frequent. (Walker *et al.* , 1991), while the MTs growing at the same rate *in vitro* do not exhibit any catastrophe. Furthermore, when experimental conditions are so adjusted as to achieve the same average elongation rate, *in vivo* MT growth is more fluctuating than *in vitro* growth in solution with Tb alone (Cassidy *et al.* , 2024). MT structure *in vivo* also differs from that of *in vitro*-polymerized MTs. In many species, including mammals, *in vitro*-polymerized MTs are known to consist of a variable number of pf (11–17 pfs). (McEwen and Edelstein, 1980, Pierson *et al.* , 1978, Scheele *et al.* , 1982, Wade *et al.* , 1990), whereas intracellular MTs are exclusively of 13 pfs. (Burton *et al.* , 1975, Scheele *et al.* , 1982, Tilney *et al.* , 1973) The percentage of 13pf-MTs *in vitro* increases when γ -TubRC is used as a template (Dendooven *et al.* , 2024) or when polymerization is performed in the presence of +TIPs such as EB1 and DCX (Moore *et al.* , 2004, Vitre *et al.* , 2008). Therefore, these templates and +TIPs are thought to be responsible for the *in vivo* 13pf formation (Chaaban and Brouhard, 2017, Evans *et al.* , 1985, Scheele *et al.* , 1982).

III. Tb-concentration dependence of chemical coupling

In Part III-1, we point out that the coupling between polymerization and GTP hydrolysis changes depending on the Tb concentration, and that they are tightly coupled in the concentration range below C_{c2} , where DI occurs. In Part III-2, we show that the data on GMPCPP MTs are compatible with the above facts. In Part III-3, we complement the concept of tight coupling with the observations at microscopic scale.

III-1. The rate of polymerization exceeds the rate of GTP hydrolysis only at Tb concentration above C_{c2} .

Previously, seemingly conflicting experimental results have been reported regarding the relationship between DI and GTP hydrolysis, but when organized according to Tb concentration, they can be summarized as shown in the title. In 1981, Carlier *et al.* simultaneously measured the amount of MT polymerization and the amount of phosphorus released by GTP hydrolysis when spontaneous MT polymerization was induced by heating a glycerol-containing Tb solution (Carlier and Pantaloni, 1981). They reported that at a Tb concentration of 17 μ M, hydrolysis and polymerization occurred simultaneously, whereas at 35 μ M, hydrolysis occurred later than polymerization (i.e., there was a time lag) (Fig. 5A).

However, subsequent measurements conducted by research groups other than Carlier *et al.* did not detect a time lag between hydrolysis and polymerization (see Appendix III-1-1), but instead highlighted the synchrony between the two (Caplow, 1992, O'Brien *et al.* , 1987, Stewart *et al.* ,

1990, Vandecandelaere et al. , 1999). In 1987, Carlier herself extended the measurement range to low Tb concentrations and remeasured the rates of polymerization and GTP hydrolysis, and acknowledged that the two were coupled for the Tb concentration range where DI occurs (Fig. 5B)(Carlier et al. , 1987). In this paper, polymerization was initiated by seeds to avoid the effects of spontaneous nucleation, and the polymerization rate was carefully compared with the average hydrolysis rate immediately after the start of the reaction. As a result, the ratio between the two is approximately 1 (=coupled) at Tb concentrations where dynamic instability is expected to occur (1.7~7 μM (Carlier et al. , 1984)), whereas the ratio exceeds 1 when the Tb concentration exceeds C_{c2} . Beyond that the ratio increases (=uncoupled more) with the Tb concentration (Fig. 5B inset) (see Appendix III-1-2). This result is roughly consistent with their results in 1981 (Fig. 5A) and with reports from other research groups (Caplow, 1992, O'Brien et al. , 1987, Stewart et al. , 1990, Vandecandelaere et al. , 1999).

Fig. 5 Tb concentration-dependence of mechano-chemical coupling

Time course of polymerization (full line) and burst of Pi liberation (symbol)(*Carlier and Pantaloni, 1981*). Tb concentrations were 34.5 (line a, filled circle) and 17.2 μM (line b, white circle). Data are normalized. (B) The initial rates of MT elongation and GTP hydrolysis measured at different Tb concentrations (*Carlier et al., 1987*). Closed symbols represent the initial rate of elongation J , and open symbols the initial rate of GTP hydrolysis J_H . Inset: change in the ratio J/J_H with Tb concentration. The ratio exceeds 1 at Tb concentration around 7 μM . (C) Summary of the regimes at different Tb concentrations. *This regime corresponds to the concentration range shown in the rightmost panel of Fig. 2. Figures in (A) and (B) are reproduced with permission from *Biochemistry*. **The exact Tb concentration dependence of catastrophe frequency around C_{C2} is not known, due to the technical difficulty.

In parallel with the development of bulk solution experiments, the so-called "GTP cap model" was presented as a mechanism for the biphasic elongation-shortening observed in DI at Tb concentrations lower than C_{C2} (*Hill and Carlier, 1983, Mitchison and Kirschner, 1984*). According to this model, "when the Tb concentration is high enough, the MT tip is capped with GTP-Tb (GTP cap), allowing the MT to continue growing. However, when the Tb concentration decreases, hydrolysis catches up with MT growth, and GDP-Tb reaches the MT tip, initiating depolymerization." (details will be discussed in Part IV). Furthermore, in 1992, *Hyman et al.* reported that "When MTs are polymerized using GMPCPP Tb, active nucleation occurs with almost no shortening" (*Hyman et al., 1992*), the result which was regarded as strong evidence supporting the GTP cap model. Hence the GTP cap model has been widely accepted by the community.

Leaving the GMPCPP Tb system observations to the next chapter (Part III-2), the remainder of this chapter will be devoted to a critical scrutinization of the process in which the experiments on bulk MT solution outlined above led to the formation of the GTP-cap model. To date, there have been no reports directly observing the nucleotide states on individual MTs, so the

introduction of some hypothesis was inevitable. Still, although unintentional, we notice two logical leaps that cannot be overlooked. The first point is that in Carlier's 1981 paper (*Carlier and Pantaloni, 1981*), in their reaction-kinetic analysis of the time evolution of turbidity (total polymerization amount) and phosphate release (total hydrolysis amount), a first-order reaction coefficient (k_1 in the paper) was assumed for the GTP-Tb uptake rate in the former. As the authors state, as was the consensus at the time, this implies fixing the number of MTs participating in polymerization, and under this assumption, the formation of GTP-Tb caps near the tips of individual MTs was suggested as an explanation for the time lag (see Box 3 for details). However, the steep rise in turbidity immediately after the start of the reaction at high Tb concentrations is due to rapid nucleation (*Ayukawa et al. , 2021, Voter and Erickson, 1984*). A time lag between polymerization and GTP hydrolysis has also been reported when MT polymerizes through rapid nucleation in the presence of Taxol (*Melki et al. , 1990*), suggesting that the time lag is a phenomenon linked to spontaneous nucleation.

The second leap in logic we consider is the use of uncoupled hydrolysis, observed only at concentrations above C_{c2} , as a transient GTP-cap to explain DI, observed only at concentrations below C_{c2} . While the tight coupling observed below C_{c2} (Fig. 5B) is important for understanding the mechanism of DI, the paper that published it (*Carlier et al. , 1987*) has not attracted as much attention as the 1981 paper (Fig. 5A), and has received fewer citations. The 1987 paper and subsequent result supporting tight coupling (*Vandecandelaere et al. , 1999*) have tended to be overlooked perhaps due to the popularity of the GTP-cap model, which assumes uncoupling.

Finally, we summarize the MT dynamics, tip structure, and Tb concentration dependence of the hydrolysis reaction seen in Parts I to III in Fig. 2 and Fig. 5C

III-2. GMPCPP Tb resembles GTP Tb but at concentration well above C_{c2} .

MTs polymerized using non-hydrolyzable GTP analogs such as GMPPNP and GMPCPP do not depolymerize or depolymerizes very slowly (*Hyman et al. , 1992, Mejillano et al. , 1990, Seckler et al. , 1990, Weisenberg and Deery, 1976*). In 1992, Hyman et al. reported that when MTs were polymerized using GMPCPP Tb, active nucleation occurred and almost no shortening occurred (*Hyman et al. , 1992*). The authors of the paper envisioned two interpretations. One is that "GMPCPP-bound Tb mimics GTP Tb in a pre-hydrolysis state in which hydrolysis is inhibited," and the other is that "GMPCPP Tb represents a special state in which the bonds between Tb are extremely strengthened" The former interpretation, in the context of "MTs that do not undergo GTP hydrolysis, escape depolymerization," was seen as supporting evidence for the GTP cap model, and the model became popular. However, even if we follow the former interpretation and accept the above context, it does not mean that "hydrolyzed MT always depolymerizes". Logically, therefore, GMPCPP-MT experiment does not implicate anything regarding the proposition, "MTs undergo depolymerization (DI) due to GTP hydrolysis", which is critical for the GTP cap model.

Another thing to keep in mind is that the C_{c2} s of GMPCPP-Tb and GTP-Tb are more than 20 times different, and the thermodynamic driving force for MT elongation of GMPCPP-Tb is much greater than that of GTP-Tb at the same concentration. From the viewpoint that GMPCPP-Tb is an analogue of GTP-Tb with only the chemical state changed, it is customary to compare the two without calibrating the Tb concentration. But from a statistical thermodynamic standpoint, the Tb concentration should be calibrated taking account of the difference in C_{c2} . For example, if experiments were conducted with both GTP-Tb and GMPCPP-Tb at 10 μ M, the experimental results for GMPCPP-Tb should not be interpreted as

mimicking 10 μ M GTP-Tb, but should be viewed as mimicking GTP-Tb at a concentration of 200 μ M ($= C_{c2}(\text{GTP}) / C_{c2}(\text{GMPCPP}) * 10$) (see Appendix III-2-1). In fact, when we compare the behavior of the GMPCPP-MTs (*Hyman et al. , 1992*) to the concentration dependence of the behavior of GTP-MT summarized in Fig. 5C, we find that the active nucleation without GTP hydrolysis in GMPCPP-MTs is parallel to the uncoupling Carlier *et al.* (*Carlier and Pantaloni, 1981*) found with GTP-MTs in the concentration range $[\text{Tb}] \gg C_{c2}$ (see Box 3), while no similarities can be found with the GTP-MTs in the concentration range $C_{c1} < [\text{Tb}] < C_{c2}$. Structurally, the shape of the tip of GMPCPP-MT is blunt, resembling the shape of GTP Tb at high concentration, $[\text{Tb}] \gg C_{c2}$ (compare Fig. 3A (50 μ M GTP-Tb) of Mandelkow 1991(*Mandelkow et al. , 1991*) with Fig. 2C of Hyman 1992 (*Hyman et al. , 1992*), Fig. 1g of Wieczorek *et al.* 2015 (*Wieczorek et al. , 2015*)). Furthermore, analysis by X-ray fiber diffraction also shows that the lattice of GMPCPP-MT is far from the compact lattice of other intermediates that appear during hydrolysis (GDP/Pi state mimicked by GDP/AlF₄⁻, GTP state mimicked by GDP/BeF₃⁻)(*Estévez-Gallego et al. , 2020*). Recent work by Liu *et al.*, who examined the packing of Tb at the growing ends of individual MT polymerized from GTP-Tb, also showed that lattice spacing of polymerizing ends is closer to the compacted state observed in GDP-MTs, rather than the extensively expanded state broadly observed in GMPCPP-MTs (*Liu et al., 2024*).

III-3. Additional information about GTP hydrolysis by microscopic observations.

As mentioned in the Introduction, dynamic instability (DI) is a non-equilibrium phenomenon maintained by the energy of hydrolysis. However, observations in bulk solution (Part III-1) that showed that MT elongation and GTP hydrolysis are synchronized at Tb concentrations below C_{c2} , where DI occurs, do not provide sufficient insight into the specific role of hydrolysis. In this section, we supplement the more microscopic observations, which suggest a correlation between GTP hydrolysis and pf-pf lateral interactions.

First, it is known that GTP hydrolysis does not occur in Tb or oligomer before MT polymerization (*David-Pfeuty et al. , 1977*). Particularly, recent measurements by Shemesh *et al.* show that although many oligomers are produced below the critical concentration required for spontaneous nucleation, GTP hydrolysis does not occur (*Shemesh et al. , 2023*) (see Appendix III-3-1). Since the one-dimensional arrangement of Tb is same in oligomers and the individual pfs at the growing end of MTs, it is highly likely that hydrolysis does not occur in the latter pfs. Manka *et al.*, who examined electron microscopy images of MTs polymerized in the presence of DCX, reported that in MTs immediately after polymerization (30 seconds after the start of the polymerization reaction), the nucleotides of β -Tb had lost Mg ions, but γ phosphate was maintained in the GDP-Pi state, and it took more time for the electron density of γ phosphate to disappear leaving GDP-MT (*Manka and Moores, 2018b*). In other words, the GTP hydrolysis reaction progresses gradually as the MT lattice matures.

GDP-MTs, formed through GTP hydrolysis, are mechanically stable owing to the multiple hydrogen bonds between pfs (*Manka and Moores, 2018b, Nogales et al. , 1999*). In contrast, MTs polymerized without GTP hydrolysis are laterally unstable: In the MTs polymerized with high concentrations of sucrose or glycerol and without GTP in solution, the tubes tend to break, exposing the sheets, and the distal pfs tend to disintegrate (*Shelanski et al. , 1973*). Alternatively, MTs can be polymerized by adding taxol to GDP-Tb (*Diaz and Andreu, 1993*). However, the flexural rigidity of these MTs is only about one-quarter that of conventional GDP-MTs (MTs) formed via hydrolysis of GTP-Tb, suggesting that the lateral bonds of former MTs are likely to be unstable (*Dye et al. , 1993, Kikumoto et al. , 2006*).

IV. An alternative view on dynamic instability

In Parts I-III, we noted the following points that the current GTP-cap model has not explicitly addressed: the presence of seed is required for DI to occur at Tb concentrations below C_{c2} (Part I); the pf curvature at the growing MT tip changes depending on Tb concentration (Part II); and uncoupling between MT growth and GTPase during DI, a premise of the GTP-cap model, does not occur at the concentrations below C_{c2} (Part III). These facts, which became clear as we look at the data along the axis of Tb concentration, guide us to the following two hypotheses regarding pfs: First, we suppose an allosteric mechanism in pf that can transmit straightening from the seed (Part IV-1). Second, MT polymerization at concentrations below C_{c2} requires coupling with GTP hydrolysis, rather than an equilibrium relaxation process as supposed in the cap model (Part IV-2). As a possible consequence of these hypotheses, we present in Part IV-3 a new scenario for DI, in which "MT growth occurs through the registration of lateral bonds between adjacent straightened pfs" (Fig. 6F). In this scenario, shortening of MT is an equilibrium relaxation process triggered by a failure of the coupling hypothesized above. The comparison with the GTP-cap model is summarized in Fig. 6.

IV-1. Seed may allosterically facilitate the growth of straight pfs

It is well-known that seeds are essential for MT growth at concentrations below C_{c2} , and their role has long been implicitly assumed to be to recruit multiple pf/oligomers together like the surface catalyst (*Rideal, 1939*). However, there are observations that cannot be explained if catastrophe frequency were constant regardless of seed: The authors of (*Gardner et al. , 2011b, Odde et al. , 1995*) have reported that catastrophes are rare immediately after growth initiation, but occur after a certain period of MT growth, whose probability increases with MT's growth.

The above authors' explanation of their observations is that catastrophe occurs after multiple "steps," and young MTs, which have just started growing, have not yet reached the number of steps susceptible for catastrophe. They named this phenomenon Memory (*Odde et al. , 1995*) or Aging (*Gardner et al. , 2011b*). However, if the observed fact has the same ground as the fact that MTs can only grow in the presence of seeds, then the issue can be simplified. We then hypothesize the following:

The pfs that make up the MT have the allosteric property of propagating curvature. A seed consisting of a stable and straight pf exerts longitudinal allosteric influences on the Tb bound to it, ultimately biasing the fluctuation between the curved and straight pfs at MT plus end toward a straight one (see Appendix IV-1-1).

The observations that straightening of the MT tip pfs is already underway before lateral interactions among pfs occur (Fig. 3I, J)(*Gudimchuk et al. , 2020*) encourages the above hypothesis, rather than the so-called "lattice model" (*Rice et al. , 2008*) in which Tb straightens by mechanical enforcement due to lateral interactions (see Appendix IV-1-2). The fact that pfs at the MT tip are much straighter than the oligomers in Tb solution also supports the allosteric influence from MTs (*McIntosh et al. , 2018*).

In the allosteric hypothesis, MT's straight, aligned tube before its tip and the curved, stable individual pfs beyond it compete through the allosteric effect that reciprocally transmits curvature. The emergence of straightened pfs (Fig. 3I, J) is then interpreted as a synergy of allosteric influences from the seed through MT (*Gardner et al. , 2011b, Odde et al. , 1995*), and

a concentration effect (Part II-2) (*Gudimchuk et al. , 2020*), which enhances the probability of pf straightening under higher Tb concentrations.

Straightening of pf leads to the suppression of catastrophe (cf. Part II), and in the same context we may interpret the increase of the time to catastrophe with increasing Tb concentration (Fig. 3B in (*Gardner et al. , 2011b*)). That the addition of MCAK leads to catastrophe of MT immediately after growth begins (Fig. 5 in the same paper) is also interpreted as the addition of MCAK favoring curved pf cancels the allosteric straightening effect from the seed (*Wieczorek et al. , 2015*) (see Appendix IV-1-3). The report by *Luchniak et al.* that depolymerization slows as the MT tip approaches the seed (*Luchniak et al. , 2023*) also suggests a antagonism between the bending-and-peeling nature of pf composed of GDP-Tb and the allosteric effect of the seed to promote pf straightening.

Structural analysis has suggested that internal modules of the Tb protein may be able to transmit the curvature of the component Tb to allosteric targets (*Ravelli et al. , 2004*). Inspired by these analyses, there is also macro-implementation research into "polymerizing" modules with an internal degree of freedom that propagates curvature (*Sekimoto, 2024*).

IV-2. Thermodynamically unfavorable growth of MT below C_{c2} may be coupled with GTP hydrolysis.

Below C_{c2} , the steady-state bulk concentration of MTs is zero (Fig. 1C, D; Part I-3), so a stable phase of MTs in thermal equilibrium is impossible. Even if nascent MTs grow from the seeds due to allosteric effects, it is unlikely that they can grow to macroscopic lengths (several micrometers) solely by this factor. MT growth must involve additional factors that actively drive it. Since hydrolysis is the only active source, we propose the following hypothesis, pushing forward the discussion in Part III-3:

Polymerization below C_{c2} is coupled to GTP hydrolysis (Fig. 5B).

The idea that GMPCPP-mediated polymerization occurs has long refuted the above idea, but as we pointed out in Part III-2, one cannot regard GMPCPP-Tb as canonical GTP-Tb involved in DI.

According to the above hypothesis, once hydrolysis and polymerization are uncoupled, the latter will not continue and those GDP-Tbs incorporated into MTs and forcibly straightened will rapidly depolymerize. (*Manka and Moores, 2018b*). The probability of occurrence of such event should naturally accumulate with MT growth. However, what causes the domino-like shortening that Mitchison and Kirschner called 'persistent depolymerization' (*Mitchison and Kirschner, 1984*) and why rescue does not occur frequently require more specific consideration. This point will be discussed in the next section, Part IV-3. In essence, the nucleotide arrangement on Tb along the pf differs during elongation and shortening.

IV-3. “lateral-latch model” as an alternative of the GTP cap model

Integrating the two hypotheses potulated in the previous chapter (the allosteric properties of pf and the coupling of polymerization with GTP hydrolysis), a molecular mechanism of MT growth can be described as follows :

At Tb concentrations below C_{C2} , when the pf proximal to the tubular MT occasionally straightens during fluctuations, transient lateral contact with the adjacent pf triggers GTP hydrolysis, which is then coupled to the establishment of stable lateral bonds. (Figs. 6D, 6F(a-c))

Fig. 6 Two possible models for the mechanism of dynamic instability. In panel A, B, D, and E, growth and shortening at the scale of MT are shown, while in panel C and F, the catastrophes at the scale of pf are shown. (A) In the GTP-cap model, MT growth is brought by the addition of GTP Tb onto its end. GTP in the β -subunit of Tb undergoes hydrolysis sometime after the Tb incorporation in MT, leaving the GTP-liganded cap at the growing end. (B) When GTP hydrolysis catches up with the MT growth and GDP Tb is exposed at the MT very end, MT starts shrinking. Stochastic binding of multiple GTP-Tbs to the tip of shrinking MT can restore GTP-cap and rescue MT growth, thus MT alternates between the growing and shrinking phase. (C) At the pf level, (a→c) the GTP-Tbs at the growing end support lateral interaction between pfs, while GTP hydrolysis induces a conformational change resulting in strain build-up within the GDP-Tb lattice. As long this configuration is maintained in 13 pf that constitute the MT, the MT can continue to grow. (d→e) As GTP hydrolysis proceeds and the last Tb becomes GDP-Tb, the GDP-Tbs release their strain, causing the whole pf to peel away. Because the lateral interactions in the adjacent

pairs of pf are interdependent, once the peeling begins in one pair, the disintegration propagates circumferentially all along the 13 pf that constitute a MT. The actual bend of pf occurs in a plane perpendicular to the plane of the paper (=perpendicular to the plane of MT wall). **(D)** In the Lateral-latch model, MT growth is initiated by the binding of GTP-Tb to the seed, followed by the lateral association of pf with the adjacent pf, which is coupled with GTP hydrolysis. **(E)** When GTP is hydrolyzed but it fails to establish lateral latch, a crack appeared between the pfs, extends toward the minus end, leading to pf unzipping and MT shrinkage. MT growth restarts from the seed, thus MT appears to go between the growing and shrinking phase. **(F)(a→b)** A single pf consists of a domain made up of straight GDP-Tb molecules, [D,st], laterally latched to an adjacent pf, and a domain made up of curved GTP-Tb molecules, [T,cv], free from the adjacent pf and exhibiting thermal bending motion in a range of curvatures. The interface between the two domains retreat one dimer towards the minus end, and this transition propagates in a domino effect, unzipping the pf and shortening the MT. As in panel C, the actual bend of pf occurs in a plane perpendicular to the plane of the paper (= a plane perpendicular to the plane the MT wall). **(G)** Comparison of the two models

The above scheme is consistent with the insight of Ravelli *et al.*, who compared the structures of curved Tb in the Stathmin-Tb complex and straight pf in the Zn-sheet (Ravelli *et al.* , 2004)

While MT growth is driven by the progressive establishment of the lateral pf-pf bond, its failure causes catastrophe. Considering that the pfs of the shortening MTs are curved outward (Fig. 3D-F), we propose the following mechanism of catastrophe:

When the part of a pf closest to the tubular MT hydrolyzes without forming a lateral bond (uncoupling), its intrinsic curvature of GDP-Tb allosterically propagates from the plus end back to the MT tubular portion, severing lateral bond one after another (=unzipping, Fig. 6E, 6F(b,d,e)).

For details of this process, including a comparison with the GTP-cap model, see the diagram in Fig. 6. We name the scenario in Fig. 6 the Lateral Latch Model (LL Model), named after the lateral bond coupled to the GTPase, the "Lateral Latch (LL)." The LL acts as a ratchet, capturing thermal fluctuations and actively rectifying the conformational change step by step. This reminds us of Feynman's ratchet wheel and pawl, a prototype of an autonomous heat engine ((Feynmann 1966); for the relationship between non-equilibrium activation processes and rare events, see BOX 3)).

In MTs, a process similar to Fig. 6F may occur at various points along the 13±1 pfs extending from the tube, resulting in growth and depolymerization of the MT cylinder. While this model shares some similarities with the Memory/Aging model (Gardner *et al.* , 2011b, Odde *et al.* , 1995), it differs from the GTP-cap model : In the LL model GTPase is coupled to the growth process, while in the GTP-cap model, GTPase is coupled to MT destabilization. The origin of this contrast lies in whether the GTP-MTs before hydrolysis is supposed to be a thermodynamically stable equilibrium state (GTP cap) or the GTP-Tb solution does the stable equilibrium state (LL). Fig. 6G describes the role of the Tb and MT phases at concentrations below Cc2 in the two models, and compares their interpretations of MT growth and collapse.

In the LL model, formation of lateral bond between pfs results in the MT growth, whereas in the GTP-cap model, binding of GTP-Tb is critical (Fig. 6G). The MT growth rate increasing

linearly with Tb concentration (Fig. 1H) (*Walker et al. , 1988*) appears to support the GTP-cap model, however, we should not dismiss those studies showing the growth rates increase nonlinearly with Tb concentration. Their graphs of growth rate vs Tb concentration exhibit a downward-convex curves (for example, a dataset for brain Tb in Fig. 2B of (*Chaaban et al. , 2018*), a dataset for the plus end in Fig. 1B of (*Strothman et al. , 2019*)). Notably, in those experiments where dynamic instability barely occur (e.g., GMPCPP-Tb (*Cleary et al. , 2022*), *C. elegans* Tb (*Chaaban et al. , 2018*), the minus end of Brain Tb (*Strothman et al. , 2019*)), growth rate increases linearly with Tb concentration.

While GTP hydrolysis occurs without delay in polymerization for Tb concentration below C_{c2} , identifying the transient sequential events occurring in the narrow space at the MT tip (Fig. 6C, F) is currently technically challenging. The following observation, which has been considered strong evidence for the GTP cap model, can also be explained by the LL model: in 1984, Mitchison and Kirschner demonstrated that when a growing MT was cleaved into multiple fragments, many of them depolymerized. They explained that the cleaved MTs lost their GTP caps and became unstable, initiating depolymerization (*Mitchison and Kirschner, 1984*). However, if we consider that the cleavage damaged the lateral interactions between pfs, and some of the MT tips could not function as seeds after cleavage, causing them to depolymerize toward the thermodynamically stable phase (Tb), then this result (and another cleavage experiment by *Walker et al. (Walker et al. , 1989)*) is also compatible with the LL model.

V. Epilogue

In this Review, we outlined how Tb concentration affects polymerization dynamics, Tb curvature, and hydrolysis. Previous studies on DI have had tendency to focus on polymerization and depolymerization as chemical reaction. However, DI is a phenomenon involving both physical conformational changes and chemical reactions and therefore must be viewed from multiple perspectives. The concepts we have built in this Review can be applied to *in vivo* MT dynamics functioning in the presence of MAPs.

We believe the following three experiments are worth pursuing in the future. First, systematically investigate by the same experimentalist the correlation between the free Tb concentration (not the initial concentration, C_0) and the distribution of both curvature of pfs at MT tip and catastrophe frequency. Second, investigate the rate of MT nucleation and GTP hydrolysis, pf curvature at MT tip, and MT lattice structure at Tb concentrations far exceeding C_{c2} , where many short MTs rapidly appear. Third, investigate the influence of seeds: When MTs are grown using GMPCPP-MTs and axonemes, is there a difference between the two seeds in the size of C_{c1} or the length MTs can grow before catastrophe? How do the pf curvature and catastrophe frequency change, depending on the distance from the seed and on Tb concentration?

BOX1: Long pfs are not curved even at their tips.

In Fig. 3I, J in the main text, we pointed out that the curvature of pf changes with length. Although the average curvatures were indifferent between growing and shrinking MTs (McIntosh *et al.*, 2018), there exist a minor population of long pfs, with small curvature appearing only in the growth phase (indicated by arrowheads in Fig. 3I).

In the paper above, the authors analyzed the pf curvature as a function of the position in pf and concluded that “pfs are most curved at their tips, and the curvature decrease linearly with distance from the pf tips” (panel **(G)** and **(H)** in this **BOX**).

However, as we calculated the average pf curvature as a function pf length for the datasets collected from the tip and from the MT-proximal end, pf curvature shows strong length dependence, independent of the position the curvature was measured (**(C)**). The mean curvature at the MT-proximal end and the tip was 19.3 ± 10.1 and 20.2 ± 12.3 degrees/dimer (mean \pm s.d.), respectively. Thus, the analysis on nearly identical datasets (**(A, B, E, F)**) led to different conclusions (**(C, D)** vs. **(G, H)**).

The discrepancy is likely due to sampling bias introduced into McIntosh's analysis method. In their analysis (**(G)**), which plotted local curvature against the distance from the tip, shorter pfs contribute only to the curvature near the tip. Therefore, the resulting graph (**(G)**) implies that "pfs with smaller lengths have larger curvatures," which is in accordance with our result (**(C)**). In any case, McIntosh *et al.* were the first to conduct extensive statistical analyses on pf curvature.

Technical notes: McIntosh *et al.* divided the entire length of the pf into short segments of approximately 2 nm each and calculated the curvature from the angular change and displacement of adjacent segments (**(J)**). We approximated their path, approximately 22 nm long, consisting of 11 2-nm segments, with a circular arc and calculated the curvature from this (**(I)**). Rather than calculating the local curvatures along the entire length of the pf, we calculated the curvature at two locations: the tip and MT-proximal end. While the difference in analytical methods may result in subtle differences in the details, it does not affect the overall properties described above. Fig.3 J shows the curvature at the MT-proximal end.

Figure for BOX1: (A and E) Traces of pfs from 37 MTs (*Gudimchuk et al.*, 2020), and 60 MTs (*McIntosh et al.*, 2018), respectively, both polymerized at the initial Tb concentration of 20 μ M from the seed of axonemal MTs. N , numbers traced. Images in A and E-G are reproduced from the original publication under a CC BY license. (B, F) Distributions of pf length for traces shown in A and E, respectively. (C) Distributions of mean curvatures for an arc with ~ 22 nm length, positioned either at tip or MT-proximal end of pfs shown in A, as a function of pf length. Error bars are SEM. (G) Distributions of mean angles between consecutive line segments in the traces shown in E, plotted as functions of distance from the pf tip. Error bars are SEM. The graphs shown in panels B and C are calculated by the authors of this review. Panel E to G are reproduced from Fig. 5 of (*McIntosh et al.*, 2018) (D, H) Schematic representation of the profile of pf curvature, depicted from the analyses in C and G, respectively. (I, J) The pf curvatures in C and G were calculated by the method shown in I and J, respectively. In I, radius and the coordinates of the center of the circle were obtained by fitting the circle to the arc constituted of 11 consecutive segments. In J, the angle between the consecutive pair of line segments that connected adjacent points of the smoothed PF tracings, $\Delta\alpha$, was measured, and the curvature K was obtained by dividing $\Delta\alpha$ by the distance between the pair, ΔS . The PF tracing was smoothed beforehand with the quadratic LOESS procedure using a 10-point span.

BOX2: Time lag between polymerization and GTP hydrolysis at high Tb concentration could be attributed mainly to MT nucleation without GTP hydrolysis.

In their 1981 paper, Carlier *et al.* reported that when the concentration of free Tb significantly exceeds C_{c2} , GTP hydrolysis occurs later than MT polymerization (Panel A). They interpreted this result as follows: "The time lag between polymerization and GTP hydrolysis is due to GTP hydrolysis occurring later than the Tb binding" (C), and this concept has been adopted in many papers today as the basis for the GTP cap model. To reach this interpretation, they put the assumption that the number of MTs is kept constant during turbidity measurements, as explained below.

Carlier *et al.* fitted the kinetic data (A) assuming that the polymerization follows a first-order reaction with the concentration of GTP-Tb in solution (with reaction rate constant k_1) and that GTP hydrolysis follows a first-order reaction with the concentration of GTP-Tb incorporated into MTs (with rate constant k_2). They showed that when Tb concentration dependence of k_1 and k_2 was set as shown in (B), their reaction model well reproduces the global features of the above experimental results (dotted and dashed curves in (A)) and the results obtained at various Tb concentrations. They introduced k_1 as a constant in the above fitting, because they thought nucleation occurs exclusively during the refractory period (which they called the "lag") before the turbidity change occurs, and that the number of MTs (M) remains constant once the turbidity starts to increase (Carlier and Pantaloni, 1978). (*1) While k_2 directly gives the rate constant for hydrolysis of GTP-Tb within the MT, the reaction rate constant k_1 gives the rate constant k_+ for the uptake of solution GTP-Tb into a single MT by $k_+ = k_1/M$. Under these settings, the Tb concentration dependence of k_1 and k_2 (B) was meant to suggest the emergence of longer GTP-cap at higher the Tb concentration (C, $[Tb]_{free} \gg C_{c2}$).

As we have only the polymerization time course as kinetic data, it is impossible to determine k_+ and M separately (Voter and Erickson, 1984)(Oosawa and Asakura, 1975). In this circumstance, the Tb concentration dependence of k_1 (B) can give different pictures (C, D), depending on how the contribution of M to k_1 is evaluated.

Contrary to Carlier's assumption that M increases only in the refractory period and the turbidity increases linearly once the turbidity starts to rise, the actual time course of turbidity increases as the square of the elapsed time in the early stage, indicating the simultaneous nucleation and elongation happen (Ayukawa *et al.*, 2021, Fygenon *et al.*, 1994). The increase in the number of MTs is more dramatic at higher free Tb concentrations, early in the reaction. Therefore, an alternative, more plausible explanation for the result shown in Panel A is that immediately after the start of the reaction, the turbidity rises due to nucleation and elongation (D, $[Tb]_{free} \gg C_{c2}$), but only a small amount of phosphate is released from those MTs that are too young to undergo GTP hydrolysis.

Melki *et al.* reported that even when MTs were polymerized by spontaneous nucleation in a solution containing Taxol, there was a time lag between polymerization and GTP hydrolysis. At the very early stage of polymerization where the gap is large, many short MTs less than 1 μm in length were generated in the solution (Figs. 4 and 5 in (Melki *et al.*, 1990). Hyman *et al.*

also reported that when MTs were polymerized using GMPCPP, a nucleotide analogue that does not hydrolyze GTP, many short MTs were rapidly formed in a very short period of time, much less than that required for GTP-MTs to appear in solution. (Fig. 1 in (Hyman *et al.*, 1992))

These observations clearly demonstrate the importance of nucleation for the rapid increase of amount of MTs, whether by high concentrations of Tb or by the addition of taxol or GMPCPP. Conversely, at Tb concentrations below C_{C2} , where spontaneous nucleation is suppressed, the putative GTP cap detected in the above experiments is unlikely to happen.

*1 In the late 1970s, the standard view (Johnson and Borisy, 1977) was that polymerization via spontaneous nucleation consisted of two discrete phases: an initial "lag" (refractory period) followed by MT growth, with nucleation occurring during the "lag." What people considered the "lag" in the 1970s and 1980s might correspond to the initial rise of a quadratic function. (Ayukawa *et al.*, 2021, Voter and Erickson, 1984) The lack of substantial change in turbidity is likely due to the short length and number of MTs. Note that the term "lag" used here is distinct from the (true) lag in which GTP hydrolysis lags behind MT polymerization.

Figure for BOX2. (A) Evolution of polymer mass, Pi burst, and the amount of GTP bound to MTs with time, normalized by the polymer mass at steady state. Shown are the values obtained in the measurements (—, ▼, ○, ●) and the values reproduced by simulation using k_1 and k_2 shown in panel B. The dashed line represents a simulation curve for Pi burst and the dotted line represents a simulation curve for the amount of GTP bound to MTs. (B) The rate constants for Tb polymerization, k_1 (●), and for GTP hydrolysis, k_2 (○), plotted as a function of Tb concentration. (C, D) The possible mechanisms for the emergence of GTP-bound MTs. The panel A and B are reproduced from the original paper (Carlier and Pantaloni, 1981) published in Biochemistry with permission.

BOX3: Why are rare events important

When dealing with an ensemble, rare events in the tail of a distribution can be more important than the mean statistics of that distribution. Such phenomena have been studied in the fields of extreme statistics (*Gumbel, 1958*), and importance sampling (for example, (*Kahn, et al., 1953*)). In the former, universal scaling laws for the distribution of extreme values in large number of samples have been discovered by choosing appropriate scaling factors and reference points. In the latter, through an appropriate change of weight those rare events are rendered to be typical events, thereby allowing for the efficient calculation of statistics for known or unknown ensembles.

Particularly, in some cases of non-equilibrium activation processes, rare states at the tail of the quasi-equilibrium fluctuation distribution of a subsystem may couple with the main system to form a bottleneck for the latter process. In the context of the main text, the long and straight pfs (during the MT growth $< C_{c2}$) and long and straight oligomers (at nucleation $\geq C_{c2}$) represent the rare events corresponding, on the one hand, to the first-passage from the rapid quasi-equilibrium fluctuations, and, on the other hand, to the directional (slow) flux leading to irreversible MT growth. The rapid extension and contraction of the pf tip reported by (*Gardner et al., 2011a*) may be fluctuations before a rare event. In physics, this may remind us of the Feynman's ratchet wheel and a pawl (*Feynman 1963*), where the pawl actively registers the rotational fluctuations of the gear step by step (see the figure below).

Schematic of Feynman's ratchet wheel and pawl (The original figure is found in his lecture book (*Feynman 1963*)). If we consider the thermal fluctuation of the vane in the high-temperature chamber on the left as the curvature of the pf, we can infer that when the straightening of the pf reaches a critical point against the bias (central load) that wants it to bend, the hydrolysis reaction advances the growth of the MT by "unit block" - just as the cooled pawl (the arrow on the right) and ratchet wheel register one rotational step.

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Appendix

This Appendix collects and presents supplementary notes to the main text. The header represents the part number, chapter number, and number in order of appearance, connected by a hyphen (-).

I-4-1: Based on the measurement of dynamic instability, Walker *et al.* calculated the Tb conc. at which the net length of MT remains zero is 10.9 μM . They thought this concentration must correspond to C_{c2} (*Walker et al., 1988*). However, Fyngenson et al. directly quantitated the

concentration where the net length change remains zero, and found that it is still lower than C_{C2} (Fygenson *et al.*, 1994).

II-1-1: The bending angles at the intradimer contacts of Tb dimers, reported to be between 10 and 13 degrees, are nevertheless for the complex with the depolymerizing factor, and they do not necessarily represent the bending angles of Tb in solution (Brouhard and Rice, 2014).

II-2-1: As mentioned in Part I-1, the distinction between free Tb concentrations and the initial Tb concentrations (C_0) is essential. The experiments in Fig. 3B and 3C were performed with C_0 of 13 μM and 20 μM , respectively (Chrétien *et al.*, 1995, McIntosh *et al.*, 2018). The experiment in Fig. 3I was conducted using the same method as in Fig. 3C at C_0 of 10 μM , 20 μM , and 40 μM (Gudimchuk *et al.*, 2020). Although the free Tb concentrations in each experiment at the time of cryofixation are unknown, the following information suggests that the free Tb concentrations of the sample in Fig. 3B were likely higher than the free Tb concentrations of the sample in Fig. 3C and Fig. 3I: (1) Pfs at C_0 of 10, 20, and 40 μM Tb (Fig. 3I) were all more curved than pfs at C_0 of 13 μM (Fig. 3B), but the pf traces in Fig. 3I show few pfs straightened to the same level as the pfs in Fig. 3B. Indeed, the authors stated, "When a few pfs extended significantly beyond others on the MT end, they sometimes showed the gentle curvature described in the literature (Chrétien *et al.*, 1995)." (Gudimchuk *et al.*, 2020). These actively growing pfs were excluded from Gudimchuk's curvature analyses. (2) The average pf length shown in Fig. 3I was less than 40 nm at all three C_0 between 10 and 40 μM . On the other hand, the average pf lengths in Fig. 3B, conducted at C_0 of 13 μM , were 165–209 nm (the diversity of average length is due to the evolution of length with time after the start of polymerization). The pf of MTs polymerized at C_0 of 40 μM in Fig. 3I was similar in both shape and length to the pf of MTs prepared at C_0 of 6.5 μM (Chrétien *et al.*, 1995).

II-2-2: McIntosh *et al.* showed that the average curvature of the tip of pf is the same whether the MT is elongated or retracted (19.3 ± 13.1 degree/dimer for growing MT, 20.2 ± 12.1 degree/dimer for shrinking MT). They also presented the data that led them to conclude that pf is most curved at the tip (McIntosh *et al.*, 2018) (see **Box 1** for details).

II-5-1: The observations of Zovko *et al.* are compatible with the *in vivo* report by McIntosh *et al.* (McIntosh *et al.*, 2018) that states that pfs are always curved, regardless of whether MTs are elongating or contracting: A closer look at McIntosh's *in vivo* data reveals that, similar to their *in vitro* data, a small number of straightened pfs appear at the tips of MTs *only* when they are growing (McIntosh 2018; compare Fig. 4D, M vs. Fig. S4D, Fig. 4P).

II-5-2 : Many results have been published from *in vitro* reconstitution experiments on the effects of +TIPs on MT growth rate, shortening rate, and frequency of catastrophe and rescue. However, the activity of +TIPs is affected by the balance with Tb concentration and the presence of other +TIPs, and the range of parameters under which the trends described here are observed is limited. Furthermore, the data on the binding sites of EB, TPX, and DCS are from the MAP-MT lattice complexes, and the structure in which these +TIPs form comets at the ends of MTs is unknown.

II-5-3 : Many *in vitro* experiments have reproduced polymerization in the presence of MAPs, but only a few have demonstrated high-speed growth comparable to that observed within cells.

III-1-1 : The fact that no time lag was detected does not exclude the possibility that a trace amount of GTP Tb below the resolution of the method for measuring MT-bound GTP remains at the tip of the MT (Stewart *et al.*, 1990).

III-1-2 : The two experiments shown in Fig. 5A, B were performed with almost the same buffer (Supplementary Table 1), and the two results can be compared without worrying about the difference in C_{c2} . The C_{c2} value under these solution conditions is unknown, but unlike the BRB buffer used by Mitchison & Kirschner and Walker to measure MT dynamics, it contains a high concentration of glycerol, so its C_{c2} value is expected to be lower than that for the BRB buffer (*O'Brien and Erickson, 1989*). In another experiment conducted in a buffer with the same composition as Fig. 5A, B, the C_{c2} value was reported to be around 3 μM (*Carlier and Pantaloni, 1978, Voter and Erickson, 1984*).

III-2-1 : If C_{C2} is the lower limit of the Tb concentration at which the (GTP-)MT phase appears stably in equilibrium thermodynamics, then the thermodynamic driving force for extension of (GTP-)MT at a free Tb concentration C_0 ($\geq C_{C2(\text{GTP})}$) may be written as $k_B T \log(C_0/C_{c2(\text{GTP})})$ per Tb dimer (in dilute solution approximation), such that it vanishes at $C_0 = C_{C2(\text{GTP})}$. Therefore, GMPCPP-Tb at a concentration of C_0 would attempt to extend MTs with a thermodynamic driving force equivalent to a GTP-Tb of $C_{C2(\text{GTP})}/C_{C2(\text{GMPCPP})}$ times C_0 . The small value of $C_{c2(\text{GMPCPP})}$ reflects the strong binding force of GMPCPP-Tb to form MTs (cf. the supplementary effect of the Tb concentration on straightening the pf at the MT tip has been considered separately (II-2)).

III-3-1 : The observations of Shemesh (*Shemesh et al. , 2023*) refute explanations that attribute the poor nucleation of MTs to GTP hydrolysis on oligomers (*Gardner, 2021, Hyman et al. , 1992*).

IV-1-1 : In the Supplementary Information, we reanalyzed the distribution of catastrophe frequencies (*Gardner et al. , 2011b*) and compared the results with a phenomenological model of catastrophe suppression that takes into account allosteric effects, with the seeds and the MTs themselves as effectors.

IV-1-2 : The angular separation between curved pfs is too large to allow their lateral interactions, except very near the base of the pf. Once the reasonably straightened pfs are laterally bound together, mechanical constraints due to lateral interactions can become a factor that promotes further straightening (*Brouhard and Rice, 2018, Guesdon et al. , 2016, Jánosi et al. , 1998*), the aspect which is consistent with the lattice model (*Rice et al. , 2008*).

IV-1-3 : Gardner *et al.* explain their results by stating, "When MCAK bends the tip of the pf and breaks the GTP cap, the catastrophe occurs in one step." (*Gardner et al. , 2011b*)

Supplementary Table

Figure # in this review	Total tubulin concentration	Seed	Buffer condition	Reference
Fig. 1C,D	Isothermal dilution from 25 μ M to 7.5 / 15 μ M PC tubulin from calf brain.	Microtubules assembled from calf brain tubulin, with the number concentration at 3.4×10^8 /ml.	80 mM K-Pipes pH 6.8, 1 mM GTP, 1mM EGTA, 1 mM MgCl ₂	Mitchison and Kirschner (1984), Fig.1.
Fig. 1E	1 - 55 μ M PC tubulin from calf brain	Axonemes with the number concentration at 10^7 /ml.	80 mM K-Pipes pH 6.8, 1 mM GTP, 1mM EGTA, 1 mM MgCl ₂	Mitchison and Kirschner (1984), Fig. 3.
Fig. 1F	17 μ M PC tubulin from calf brain		90mM Pipes pH 6.9, 2.7 mM GTP, 1.8 mM EGTA, 0.9 mM MgSO ₄	Horio and Hotani (1986), Fig. 2.
Fig. 1G-J	7 - 15.5 μ M PC tubulin from porcine brain.	Axonemes with the number concentration of 2.7×10^7 /ml.	100mM Pipes pH6.9, 1 mM GTP, 2 mM EGTA, 1mM MgSO ₄ .	Walker et al (1988), Fig. 4 - 7.
Fig. 3A	50 μ M, PC tubulin from porcine brain		100 mM NaPipes pH6.9, 1mM GTP, 1 mM EGTA, 1 mM MgSO ₄ , 1 mM DTT. Microtubules were assembled in a test tube and applied to the grid.	Mandelkow et al. (1991), Fig. 1.
Fig. 3B	13 μ M PC tubulin from calf brain.	centrosome (1×10^8 /ml)	80 mM Pipes, pH6.9, 1 mM GTP, 1 mM EGTA, 1 mM MgCl ₂ , MT assembly was conducted on the grid at 37C.	Chretien et al. (1995), Fig. 4.
Fig. 3C	20 μ M porcine brain tubulin	Axoneme (concentration unreported)	80 mM Pipes, pH6.9, 1 mM GTP, 1 mM EGTA, 1 mM MgCl ₂ , MT assembly was conducted on the grid at 37C.	McIntosh et al. (2018) et al., Fig. 5D, F.
Fig. 3D	Isothermal dilution, porcine brain tubulin		100 mM NaPipes pH6.9, 1mM GTP, 1 mM EGTA, 1 mM MgSO ₄ , 1 mM DTT. Microtubules were assembled in a test tube and applied to the grid.	Mandelkow et al. (1991), Fig. 2a.
Fig. 3E	Isothermal dilution, calf brain tubulin	centrosome (1×10^8 /ml)	80 mM Pipes, pH6.9, 1 mM GTP, 1 mM EGTA, 1 mM MgCl ₂ , MT assembly was conducted on the grid at 37C.	Chretien et al. (1995), Fig. 5.
Fig. 3F	Isothermal dilution (likely below 3 μ M), porcine brain Tubulin.	Axoneme (concentration unreported)	80 mM Pipes, pH6.9, 1 mM GTP, 1 mM EGTA, 1 mM MgCl ₂ , MT assembly was conducted on the grid at 37C.	McIntosh et al. (2018), Fig. 7A.
Fig. 3G	20 μ M porcine brain tubulin	Axoneme (concentration unreported)	80 mM Pipes, pH6.9, 1 mM GTP, 1 mM EGTA, 1 mM MgCl ₂ , MT assembly was conducted on the grid at 37C.	McIntosh et al. (2018), Fig. 5G.
Fig. 3H	< 3 μ M porcine brain Tubulin	Axoneme (concentration unreported)	80 mM Pipes, pH6.9, 1 mM GTP, 1 mM EGTA, 1 mM MgCl ₂ , MT assembly was conducted on the grid at 37C.	McIntosh et al. (2018), Fig. 7E.
Fig. 3I, J	10, 20, 40 μ M porcine brain tubulin	Axoneme (concentration unreported)	80 mM Pipes, pH6.9, 1 mM GTP, 1 mM EGTA, 1 mM MgCl ₂ , MT assembly was conducted on the grid at 37C.	Gudimchuck et al. (2020), Fig. 5d.
Fig. 4A	Recombinant <i>Drosophila</i> α 1 β 1 tubulin at 10 to 30 μ M for WT, 2 to 5 μ M for β -Y222F mutant. The C ₂ is 4.7 μ M (WT) and 0.19 μ M (Y222F).		80 mM Pipes, pH6.8, 1 mM EGTA, 2 mM MgCl ₂ , 1 mM GTP, MT assembly was conducted at 25C.	Ayukawa et al. (2021), Fig. 1I, J, K.
Fig. 4B, C	Recombinant <i>Drosophila</i> α 1 β 1 tubulin at 10 μ M for WT, 5 μ M for β -Y222F mutant.		80 mM Pipes, pH6.8, 1 mM EGTA, 2 mM MgCl ₂ , 1 mM GTP, MT assembled in a test tube was transferred to the grid.	Ayukawa et al. (2021), Fig. 2E, G.
Fig. 4D	Recombinant <i>Drosophila</i> α 1 β 1 tubulin at 5 μ M for β -Y222F mutant.		80 mM Pipes, pH6.8, 1 mM EGTA, 2 mM MgCl ₂ , 1 mM GTP, MT assembled in a test tube was transferred to the grid.	Ayukawa et al. (2021), Fig. 6A - L.
Fig. 5A	17.2 and 34.5 μ M porcine brain tubulin.		50 mM Mes, pH6.6, varying amount of GTP (100-200 μ M), 6 mM MgCl ₂ , 0.5 mM EGTA, 3.4 M Glycerol.	Carlier and Pantaloni (1981), Fig. 3.
Fig. 5B	1.7 ~ 20 μ M of PC tubulin purified from Porcine brain.	Microtubules assembled with Me ₂ SO from porcine brain tubulin, with the number concentration at $1.2-1.8 \times 10^{11}$ /ml.	50 mM Mes, pH6.8, 20 or 100 μ M GTP, 6 mM MgCl ₂ , 0.5 mM EGTA, 3.4 M Glycerol.	Carlier et al. (1987), Fig. 4.

Summary of the experimental conditions for the results presented in the figures. Each figure is reprinted from respective journal with permission.

Supplementary File 1

Allosteric nature of seed is suggested by the data of catastrophe

Goal and message:

We re-derive catastrophe frequency from the published data on lifetime to catastrophe (*Chaaban et al. , 2018, Gardner et al. , 2011b*). We do so using a slightly different but essentially equivalent method from their original work, and over a broader range than previously. We then present a phenomenological model in which a "factor" that prevents catastrophe is allosterically transmitted from the seed through the pf, and evaluate the model by comparing it with the data. Finally, we provide an explanation for the fact that "seeds are essential for MT elongation below C_{c2} " through this model.

Introduction of basic variables:

First, let us introduce basic variables that can be extracted, without a model, solely from the experimental data in Fig. 1B of (*Gardner et al. , 2011b*) and Fig. 2D of (*Chaaban et al. , 2018*) mentioned above in Part IV-2, IV-4. The notations used are those used in the above references. In the following description, for simplicity of notation, we will use the well-known fact that the elongation rate at a given Tb concentration is independent of MT length (typically around 15 nm/sec, (*Gardner et al. , 2011b*)) so that the age t , the time since a MT began to elongate from the seed, also represents the length of the MT by using appropriate units of length and time.

$f_{\pm}(s) ds$: the probability that a MT with current age s will experience a catastrophe within a small time span $[s, s+ds]$. $f_{\pm}(t)$ is called the catastrophe frequency. This is the most fundamental quantity that directly represents the instability of the tip of a MT with length t .

$F(t)$: the probability that the lifetime (until a catastrophe) of a single MT that has begun to grow is less than t . By definition, $F(0) = 0$. Therefore, $1-F(t)$ gives the probability that no catastrophe has occurred until age t . This is not independent of $f_{\pm}(s)$, but related through the relation:

$$1 - F(t) = e^{-\int_0^t f_{\pm}(s) ds} \quad (1)$$

This is because "avoiding catastrophe until time t " (left-hand side) is equivalent to "not causing a catastrophe during the time span $[s, s+ds]$ " for any s ($0 \leq s < t$) (right-hand side).

Length distribution in steady state:

The above information, f_{\pm} and F , are cohort-specific. However, if the onset of elongation occurs statistically randomly and uniformly over time within a batch, $F(t)$ is known to be related to the distribution of age (i.e., current length), not lifespan, of the MT population as follows:

$$q_+(s) = \alpha[1 - F(s)] \quad (2)$$

where, the proportionality constant $\alpha=q_+(0)$ is determined so that the normalization of the probability distribution, $\int_0^{\infty} q_+(s) ds = 1$, is satisfied. More concretely, $\alpha = \left(\int_0^{\infty} [1 - F(s)] ds\right)^{-1}$. (2) can be understood by considering that those MTs that began growing s seconds ago and have survived to the present contribute to $q_+(s)$. In any case, if $F(s)$ is known, $q_+(s)$ can be determined without census-like measurements. Equation (2) can then be called the "cohort-population relationship." Also, note that $dF(t)/dt$ is the distribution of lifetime t (number of catastrophe events at time t), which is often used, but is not the catastrophe frequency, $f_{\pm}(s)$. The relationship between the two is given by (1) above, or its rewritten form, Eq. (1) in (*Gardner et al. , 2011b*), i.e., $f_{\pm}(t) = \frac{dF(t)/dt}{1 - F(t)}$. Compared to f_{\pm} , $dF(t)/dt$ also includes the surviving fraction, $1-F(t)$.

From Experimental Data of $F(t)$ to Fundamental Variables $f_{\pm}(t)$:

The above describes the fundamental variables and their interrelationships. What properties does $f_{\pm}(t)$ exhibit when applied to the experimental data of $F(t)$ in (*Gardner et al. , 2011b*) ? In the Gardner's paper, the cumulative probability $F(t)$ obtained from numerous kymographs (Fig. 1A) is shown in Fig. 1B. The steady-state MT length distribution, $q_+(s)$, is also shown up to approximately 400 sec (6000 nm) (Fig. 6A, right panel). While their derivation method of $q_+(s)$ is unknown, we used Equation (2) above to directly obtain the results for $q_+(s)$ over a wider range (Fig. SI1-(a) top) from $F(t)$. The horizontal axis is seconds. Fig.SI1-(a) bottom shows the same operation performed on Chaaban's data ((*Chaaban et al. , 2018*), Fig.2D). In both cases, the cumulative probability vs t begins from plateau, and the above authors were the first to show that catastrophes are suppressed in short MTs. If the catastrophe frequency f_{\pm} were constant, the frequency distribution $q_+(t)$ would have been exponential and would not have had an initial plateau. (Furthermore, if the original GTP-cap model were applied to MTs approximated by a single pf, the decline would have been even steeper than exponential (calculation not shown).)

Still more information can be obtained by extracting the catastrophe frequency, $f_{\pm}(t)$. The derivation route we adopted involves first rewriting (1) as follows:

$$\int_0^t f_{\pm}(s)ds = -\ln[1 - F(t)] \quad (3)$$

and substituting the experimental data $F(t)$ into the right-hand side. The right-hand side of equation (3) plotted from the (*Gardner et al. , 2011b*), Fig.1B) and (*Chaaban et al. , 2018*), Fig.2D) data is shown in Fig. SI1-(b), as a series of red dots, being read out manually from the figures. Three characteristics are evident from this data: (i) at $t = 0$, it starts to increase from horizontal, (ii) then the increase tapers off midway, and (iii) it approaches a final asymptote. Since the derivative of the right-hand side of equation (3) is the catastrophe frequency, $f_{\pm}(t)$, we can translate these three characteristics into the behavior of, $f_{\pm}(t)$. That is, (i) $f_{\pm}(t)$ increases from a small value at a short MT, (ii) then experiences an intermediate maximum (bump), and (iii) approaches a final constant value. The above can be read from the data without assuming any model.

Features the model should reproduce:

We think that a model of the catastrophe frequency $f_{\pm}(t)$ of MT growth in solutions below C_{c2} should imply the basic premise (0) that MTs cannot begin to grow without a seed, and also provide an explanation for (i, ii, iii) above. Gardner *et al.*, based on the GTP-cap model, introduced the hypothesis that "two or more defects are required to break a growing MT," reproducing (i) above, i.e., the suppression of the catastrophe frequency for short MTs, and (iii) above, i.e., the asymptotic trend toward a constant catastrophe frequency for long MTs. But (0) above, i.e., the necessity of a seed, was left unquestioned. (cf. We could not examine (ii)'s bump (Fig. SI1-(c) top), as their right panel in Fig. 6A cuts off just near the bump.)

Fig.SI1-a,b,c (a) MT length distribution in a system undergoing steady cycles of elongation and catastrophe. (b) Experimental values of the right-hand side of equation (3) (red dots), and the fitted curve (blue line) calculated using equations (4) and (5) for the left-hand side of equation (3). (c) Catastrophe frequency plotted against MT age/length by differentiating the fitted curve in (b). The top row of figures is based on data adapted from ((*Gardner et al. , 2011b*), Fig.1B). The horizontal axis is in seconds. The peak occurs around 400 seconds (corresponding to a length of approximately $6\mu\text{m}$). The concentration is $15\mu\text{M}$. The bottom row of figures is based on data adapted from ((*Chaaban et al. , 2018*), Fig.2D) for brain Tb at $7.5\mu\text{M}$. The horizontal axis is in minutes.

Allosteric model implying the necessity of seed:

We would rather focus our phenomenological analysis of the above data on the role of seed. If the seed were simply a chemisorption site that initiates MT growth, as in the Eley-Rideal mechanism for heterogeneous catalysis, it would be impossible to protect MTs against catastrophe up to a length of a few micrometers. Therefore, we first hypothesize that the seed exerts a nonlocal, i.e., allosteric interaction that favors the straightening of nearby pfs that make up the MT, thereby protecting the MT tip from catastrophe. Furthermore, it is consistent to assume that the MT, which is the medium through which the allosteric interaction is transmitted, also contributes as effector of the allosteric effect on the tip.

Specifically, we assume an "allosteric stabilization barrier" $\Delta(t)$ such that the catastrophe frequency at the tip of a MT of length t can be written as

$$f_{\pm}(t) = f_0 e^{-\Delta(t)}. \quad (4)$$

The barrier is not purely energetic, and the exponential function is not equilibrium Boltzmann weight; it is a phenomenological object that also includes the effects of GTP hydrolysis. Thinking that the protection against catastrophe by the seed and the MT are multiplicative, we assume the following form with Δ_0 , Δ_{∞} , λ_s , λ_b as positive parameters,

$$\Delta(t) = \Delta_0 e^{-\lambda_s t} + \Delta_{\infty} (1 - e^{-\lambda_b t}) \quad (5)$$

The first term on the right-hand side of (5) represents the direct contribution of the seed as an effector over a distance of $\sim \lambda_s$ to the barrier. The second term is in fact the integral $\int_0^t \Delta_{\infty} e^{-\lambda_b u} \lambda_b du$, where $\Delta_{\infty} e^{-\lambda_b u} \lambda_b du$ in the integral represents a similar effect in which the MT line element du at a distance of u ($0 \leq u < t$) from the MT tip contributes to the barrier as an allosteric effector. The internal degrees of freedom of the Tb constituting the MT are actually responsible for allostery, and interfaces between Tbs along pf connect these internal degrees of freedom (*Sekimoto, 2024*). Fig.SI2 illustrates the Allosteric model described here in comparison with the Aging/Memory model of (*Gardner et al. , 2011b*).

Fig.SI2 Schematic representation of catastrophe mechanism according to (a) Aging/Memory model (b) Allosteric model.

Now, we adjusted the positive parameters Δ_0 , Δ_∞ , λ_s , λ_b in equation (5) so that, if we calculate the left side of equation (3) through (4) and (5) to well approximate the right side of equation (3) from the experimental data. With those parameter values we plot the resulting catastrophe frequency, $f_{\pm}(t)$ (see equation (4)), as shown in the upper and lower figures of Fig.SI1-(c). As long as the fit of equation (3) is good, this result should not depend on the model or interpretation. In particular, the function in equation (5) itself may or may not bring about a bump in $f_{\pm}(t)$ depending on the values of the ratios Δ_∞/Δ_0 and λ_b/λ_s , so the bump is not the artifact of the allostery model.

The results in the top and bottom graphs of Fig.SI1-(c) show all of the features (i, ii, iii) that we have already observed from the experimental data (the red dots in Fig.SI1-(b)). What we emphasize even more is that the allostery model allows to explore the case where the seed is absent ($\Delta_0 = 0$). The results are shown in Fig.SI3, along with the case where the seed is present. When the seed is absent (blue), the catastrophe frequency, $f_{\pm}(t)$, quasi-explodes at $t=0$, and MTs effectively cannot grow at all.

Fig.SI3 The effect of seed on the relationship, $f_{\pm}(t)$ vs t . Orange curve: seeded ($\Delta_0 \neq 0$) case (same as the previous Fig. SI1-(c) top). Blue curve: without seeded ($\Delta_0 = 0$) case, where $f_{\pm}(t=0)=470$.

In the above discussion, we have focused on the context of MT growth, and have seen the constructive effect of allosteric interactions, i.e., the propagation of straightening toward the pf at the MT tip. However, since allosteric interactions are reciprocal, if the curvature of the pf at the MT tip increases, it can have a destructive effect toward the MT base (see IV-4).

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